

UNLOCKING AZERBAIJAN'S EXPORT CAPABILITIES: PATHWAYS TO GROWTH**Sanan Babishov**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14277109>**Abstract**

The purpose of the research - The main purpose of the research is to open the export opportunities of Azerbaijan and to determine the directions of development in this process.

Methodology of the research - In the methodology of the research, official statistical data were included and analyzes were carried out. Also, the determination of development directions was based on the analysis of foreign and local publications.

Application importance of the research - it is important from the point of view of studying the export opportunities of Azerbaijan and determining the directions of development, the current investment projects in our Republic are directed to the non-oil and gas sector. Determining export opportunities is important in terms of which areas to focus on with investments and projects in this area.

Results of the study - As a result of our study, the mention of export opportunities in Azerbaijan can be used by researchers in the development of this field.

Originality and scientific innovation of the research - This research includes the analysis of the latest information and statistical indicators about export opportunities and directions in Azerbaijan. In addition, it reflects the importance of the export process and the analysis of development directions.

Keywords: Export opportunities, Azerbaijan trade, development direction, economic perspective.

Introduction

The experiences of the countries of the world confirm that in modern times, no country can stay outside the international trade system and ensure the development of the national economy without export-import transactions. The development of national economies directly depends on the effective participation of countries in the international division of labor, the overall organization of international integrations, and the effective use of the export potential of real sectors of the economy.

Currently, the acceleration of globalization processes in the economy has made it necessary for countries to actively participate in international economic specialization. The modern development of the world economic system embodies the further expansion and development of international trade, its liberalization, the dynamic change of trade and economic relations between countries from year to year in terms of both geographical and commodity structure.

One of the most important economic problems facing our country after gaining independence was organizing the country's integration into the world economy, establishing foreign trade relations, increasing the export potential and using these processes effectively. In the first years, the economy of our republic was mainly dependent on imports, and such deep crisis processes were observed in the areas that formed the priority of the economy over time. However, today the situation is completely different, rapid development processes are observed in the country's economy, great achievements have been made in the direction of the integration of our national economy into the world economy, and the number of countries with which trade and economic relations have been established has reached 150. During 2009-2015, the volume of foreign trade turnover increased more than 13 times. Thus, over

the years, the import has increased more than 1 times, and the export has increased up to 16 times.

Currently, the acceleration of integration processes and the expansion of foreign economic relations are turning our national economy into an integral part of the world economy. The specialization of our country in the fields where it has comparative advantages, the production of internationally competitive export products in these sectors, and the establishment of the foreign trade strategy in a way that serves the national economic development have become one of the most urgent problems of the modern era.

It should be noted that 90-95 percent of the country's exports are oil and oil products. Oil production in the country is planned to reach 32 million tons in 2014, and 50 million tons in 2015-2016. So, in the coming years, oil export and its weight in foreign trade will increase even more. Natural gas exports are expected to increase rapidly in the coming years. The transformation of Azerbaijan into a large-scale hydrocarbon exporter and the inflow of large amounts of foreign exchange reserves from this field necessitated the implementation of an economic policy based on deep scientific research in order to insure against the negative trends observed in a number of other oil exporting countries, especially the threat of a decrease in the export potential of other real sectors of the economy. Both the international experience and the economic strategy formed by the state show that the priority of the efficient use of foreign exchange reserves received from oil exports is the development of non-oil sectors and the increase of the export potential of these areas. At present, the issue that worries scientific economists more and is the subject of deep scientific discussions and debates is exactly how and in what ways this is implemented.

Most developing nations rely on natural resources and primary commodities for export income, with the industrial sector contributing minimally to their economies. Revenue derived from natural resources and primary commodities is not a dependable foundation for sustainable economic growth, as export revenues from these resources lack competitiveness due to the inelasticity of their supply. Furthermore, fluctuations in their prices result in significant income volatility, contributing to elevated risk and uncertainty. Natural resources and basic commodities can serve as inputs for high value-added industrial sectors, hence enhancing economic growth. Economists assert that for poor countries to achieve sustained economic growth and development, they must transition from exporting basic goods produced with rudimentary technology to producing and exporting high-tech commodities.

This notion has been substantiated by endogenous growth theories, particularly the principle of "learning by doing." These ideas claim that the accumulation of knowledge enhances productivity, thereby fostering economic growth. The experiences of industrialized and affluent nations demonstrate that their economic advancement correlates with the growth of high-technology firms and services. In the early 1990s, rich economies experienced the emergence of high-technology businesses, referred to as third-wave economic development. Consequently, it appears that the trajectory of national development is contingent upon the advancement of high-tech sectors. The domestic product market, particularly the industrial sector in developing nations, encounters constraints. Under such circumstances, even if developing nations want to industrialization, their domestic markets will be unable to accommodate the increasing quantity of industrial goods. Conversely, it has been challenging, especially for industrialized nations, to compete in the market for primary and traditional industrial products. In this context, enhancing the competitiveness of firms in global marketplaces and securing a greater market share can be achieved through the production and sale of industrial goods, particularly high-tech products. An examination of the statistical data reveals the significant advancement of many emerging nations, including China, Hong Kong, Korea, Singapore, Vietnam, Malaysia, Mexico, and Thailand, in the exportation of high-technology businesses. Notwithstanding the rise in high technology exports, the impact of this variable on the economic growth of developing nations remains inadequately researched. Furthermore, research has not addressed the concurrent examination and comparison of this effect between emerging and wealthy nations.

Main part

According to Fu (2004), export-led growth processes require several preconditions. Therefore, the preconditions for the success of export-led growth can be summarized as follows:

- For the success of export-led growth, it is necessary not to consider the export sector in isolation from the rest of the economy. Growth in manufacturing exports, which generally benefits inputs produced in the local economy, provides a strong incentive for expansion

in input sub-industry industries. When development in the export sector is largely driven by commercial transactions, the linkages between export and non-export sectors are likely to be limited. This situation may arise when Export-Processing Zones (EPZ) are used to encourage foreign capital (CountRIES, E. B. D. 2024). Export-Processing Zones may remain as a separate foreign enclave with less impact on the rest of the economy. These zones lead to freer trade. Therefore, Export-Processing Zones are a measure of the nature of second-best policy (Huang, R., 2024). As a result, it cannot be expected that this will always be useful. The increase in welfare benefits the economy, especially the economy due to the increase in nature and factor flows, and the relations between the economy and other settlement areas and other economies (Öncel, A., Saidmurodov, S., Kutlar, A. 2024). The opportunity cost of locally owned resources for direct investment incentives in regions in the domestic economy and the relative productivity of foreign firms compared to local firms are important determinants of the increase in welfare (Peterson, M., & Downie, C. 2024). If the social opportunity cost of labor moving from the economy to the region is zero, the benefit to the economy of establishing a Processing/Manufacturing Zone for Export Sales will be positive. The spillover effects of these zones will probably be low when combined with imported goods and elements. In addition, the status and structure of domestic economic development will be related to the technological spillover effects in these regions (Sah, A. K., Sah, D. K., et.al 2024).

- Production techniques in the export sector may be more advanced than those in use before. If the technology in the export sector is no different from the rest of the economy or if the expansion in the export sector occurs without any change in the production function, the spillovers to the rest of the economy will be low during periods when technology is transferred. Positive linkages may arise from exports requiring skilled labor rather than unskilled labor (Sanches-Antônio, L. D., 2024). The need for talent in exports can create greater incentives for human capital accumulation through education. In addition, job training in the export sector can be spread through labor flows in other sectors, and skilled labor can be a source of entrepreneurship. However, effective assimilation of export spillovers depends on basic development elements such as infrastructure facilities, large entrepreneurs, and human capital accumulation in the domestic economy. In other words, a minimum level of development is necessary for the impact of exports on growth.

- A high share of exports in total output and, to a large extent, a high growth rate of exports are another prerequisite for export-led growth (Sojoodi, S., Baghbapour, J., 2024).

- The level and structure of development in trading partners can strongly affect the impact of growth on exports. When two-way trade patterns are strongly biased toward technological leadership, knowledge spillovers will be stronger. Spillovers between countries will be high in industries with large R&D expenditures (Srdelić, L., & Dávila-Fernández, M. J., 2024).

- If growth in the export sector depends on labor migration from other sectors and other parts of the economy, the impact of exports on balanced growth in the economy will depend on profits and migration costs in the home and host regions (Susanto, P. C., Subagio, M., et.al 2024).

- Export expansion occurs as a result of trade liberalization. The order of liberalization will affect growth in the economy. The generally recommended order of liberalization is to start with gradual quantitative restrictions (quotas), then move on to tariffs and devaluation, and finally to liberalization in capital markets. This order is important in terms of providing the right transmission mechanisms for export-led growth (Topcu, B. A., 2011).

Export opportunities of Azerbaijan

One of the points of special importance in the general economic development is the introduction of high-quality domestically produced products that meet international standards to world markets, and the strengthening of the export potential. This is also one of the main factors affecting the faster development of relations with foreign trade partners of any country, deepening of international cooperation. The development of export opportunities on an ever-increasing line is one of the main directions of the economic policy implemented in our country. In this sense, the decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, on May 14 of this year, aimed at taking additional measures in the field of improving the regulations of import-export transactions, is of particular importance. First of all, because the said decree is necessary in terms of adapting and simplifying the import-export procedures to today's requirements of economic development. Also, the additions and changes made to the "Regulations of import-export operations in the Republic of Azerbaijan" by the said decree serve to more efficiently use the export potential.

For several years now, Azerbaijan has been one of the leading countries not only in the region, but also in the world in terms of economic growth rate. Even now, Azerbaijan maintains its leading position in this direction. Due to the successful continuation of the development strategy based on national leader Heydar Aliyev by his worthy successor Mr. Ilham Aliyev, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the relevant measures taken, and the reforms implemented, the dynamic progress of Azerbaijan will be ensured in the coming period. Against the background of the country's large energy reserves, the successful implementation of the economic diversification policy, state support for entrepreneurship, programs that include the development of regions, steps that serve the rapid progress of the non-oil sector, and the necessary reforms carried out in accordance with the requirements of the time are further strengthening the economic positions of Azerbaijan. The logical result of the above is that the volume of total production in our country is constantly increasing, and new production areas and enterprises are being formed. This also determines the fact that the products once imported by Azerbaijan are now becoming a source of export.

As for the indicators characterizing the economic development, it should be noted first of all that the volume of the gross domestic product in our country increased by 2.8 times only during the years 2004-2009. Even in 2009, when the global financial and economic crisis reached its peak, real GDP growth was 9.3 percent. During this period, 3.5 percent growth was achieved in agriculture, 13.1 percent in communication, 9.9 percent in trade, and 9.3 percent in transport.

First of all, comprehensive measures are taken in accordance with relevant state programs regarding the development of regions where non-oil potential is concentrated. In addition, state support measures that encourage the development of entrepreneurship, including the exemption of agricultural product producers from all taxes except land tax until 2014, providing subsidies to agricultural product producers, fertilizer and agricultural machinery on preferential terms through "Agroleasing" OJSC provision of special economic zones, simplification of regulatory and administrative procedures, further improvement of the business and investment environment, creation of industrial towns, business incubators and other measures are of particular importance in expanding production and increasing export opportunities in our country.

The creation of these complexes contributes to the development of the country's economy by providing food security, socio-economic development of regions and increasing investment attractiveness, intensive development of agriculture, prevention of crop loss, protection of the internal market, protection of consumers' rights, introduction of new technologies and increase of export potential. will make great contributions. Thus, in terms of efficient use of the export potential of agricultural products, it is important to provide it with appropriate storage conditions as well as the production of a product. The built refrigerators and grain warehouses enable the extension of the market access period of agricultural products and instead of exporting the product at a cheap price during the production season, it can be stored for a certain period and exported at a more reasonable price.

At the same time, the joining of our country to the Generalized System of Preferences (GSP) should be considered as a serious step taken in terms of expanding access opportunities for entrepreneurs to existing and new export markets. As you know, our country has the right to use the GSP programs of Canada, Japan, Turkey, Norway, Switzerland and the United States of America, and the GSP+ programs of the European Union and export its products to the markets of those countries on preferential terms. So, in order to better express the advantages of GSP, it should be noted that the Republic of Azerbaijan, by joining the GSP program of the United States in December 2008, was granted preferential treatment to those countries on 3473 goods and by joining the GSP+ program of the European Union. got the opportunity to export.

In order to ensure that our entrepreneurs use these opportunities more effectively, informative seminars on export opportunities within the framework of the GSP system were organized in Baku city and regions, and information on the possibilities of using the system

was published. It is also planned to conduct training-seminars on the possibilities of using the GSP system, purchase and sale agreements in international trade, delivery conditions, transportation and logistics topics,

improvement of export certification procedures, organization of business forums and more intensive implementation of other events.

Methodology

Table 1. Dynamics of export of basic goods

Products	2023	
	Amount	Amount, thousand US dollars
Potatoes, tons	71,192.3	30,930.3
Fresh vegetables, tons	178,792.0	180,587.2
Fresh fruit, tons	454,856.0	502,107.7
River, tons	731.5	6,605.0
Vegetable oils, tons	5,492.4	9,214.3
Hydrogenated fats and oils, tons	3,141.5	6,397.2
Margarine, other edible mixtures, ton	3,055.0	5,030.5
Crude oil, thousand tons	26,047.3	16,240,829.6
Crude oil, according to the reports of SOCAR and ABES, thousand tons	26,068.0	15,478,434.7
Kerosene fuel for jet engines, thousand tons	108.7	109,565.6
Heavy distillates or gasoils for other purposes, thousand tons	718.9	380,152.8
Natural gas, million cubic meters	26,623.5	13,678,344.1
Natural gas, according to the reports of SOCAR and ABES, million cubic meters	24,933.5	10,259,885.9
Liquid fuel, thousand tons	1.1	545.8

Source: <https://www.stat.gov.az/source/trade/>

Azerbaijan's export data for 2023 has a large share of crude oil and natural gas, the volume of crude oil is 16 billion US dollars, which has an important share in its country's economy. Also, fruits and vegetables have high export values of 502.1 million US dollars and 180.6 million US dollars, respectively, which forms the

conclusion that agriculture is an important sector in Azerbaijan's trade portfolio. Other notable exports include vegetable oils, margarine and hydrogenated oils, suggesting a diversified agricultural sector in addition to raw materials.

Graph 1. Export of important types of products in 2023 (by country) Potatoes, tons

Source: <https://www.stat.gov.az/source/trade/>

Azerbaijan's potato export data shows high trade relations with Russia, which accounts for the majority of exports at 62,642.2 tons and is worth 28,081.0 thousand US dollars. This is followed by smaller amounts

to Ukraine (5,450.3 tons), Belarus (2,173.8 tons) and Kazakhstan (483.9 tons). Relations with Russia are noted as an important trading partner, while relations with other countries are lower.

Table 2. Fresh vegetables, tons

	Amount	Amount, thousand US dollars
Total	178,792.0	180,587.2
Russia	156,501.4	169,767.8
Georgia	9,113.9	1,975.5
Ukraine	8,677.0	2,863.4
Belarus	1,661.6	3,363.6
Poland	1,173.5	1,702.5
Iraq	1,160.1	438.6
Moldova	243.1	94.4
Other countries	261.4	381.4

Source: <https://www.stat.gov.az/source/trade/>

Azerbaijan's fresh vegetable export data is dominated by Russia, which accounts for more than 90% of the total volume of 156,501.4 tons. Georgia, Ukraine and Belarus are smaller importers, with smaller shares,

for example, Georgia comes in at 9,113.9 tonnes at US\$1.98 million and Ukraine at 8,677 tonnes at US\$2.86 million. Exports to other countries, such as Poland, Iraq and Moldova, remain minimal both in terms of volume and value.

Table 3. Fresh fruit, tons

	Amount	Amount, thousand US dollars
Total	454,856.0	502,107.7
Russia	404,198.9	414,831.1
Ukraine	18,430.5	13,666.7
Kazakhstan	10,713.7	5,763.6
Germany	3,673.6	22,208.6
Uzbekistan	3,217.6	4,588.4
Italy	2,673.1	15,713.4
Belarus	2,300.0	2,959.7
Georgia	2,255.9	2,065.2
Other countries	7,392.7	20,311.0

Source: <https://www.stat.gov.az/source/trade/>

Azerbaijan's fresh fruit export data for 2023 show that it is significantly dependent on Russia, it was worth 414.8 million US dollars, which is more than 80% of

the total value. Ukraine is USD 13.7 million and Kazakhstan is USD 5.8 million. Although Germany and Italy imported 3,673.6 and 2,673.1 tons respectively, they reflect a higher value per ton, which indicates the high quality of products. constitutes a ton.

Table 4. Crude oil, thousand tons

	Amount	Amount, thousand US dollars
Total	26,047.3	13,240,829.6
Italy	11,117.5	7,077,115.4
Israel	2,270.3	1,394,267.6
India	2,025.1	1,227,040.9
Germany	1,341.0	871,933.8
Spain	1,222.0	769,586.8
Turkey	1,202.2	676,306.6
Czechia	1,136.0	682,886.7
Croatia	975.2	590,404.9
Greece	743.5	455,309.0
United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	691.0	432,278.6
Ireland	630.1	366,641.2
Romania	621.9	382,756.7
Other countries	2,071.5	1,314,301.4

Source: <https://www.stat.gov.az/source/trade/>

Azerbaijan's crude oil exports are important and have a high share in European markets, and Italy as the largest importer of these countries bought 11,117.5

thousand tons of oil worth 7.08 billion US dollars, which is more than 50% of the total export value. Israel, India and Germany each have transactions worth 800

million US dollars. Spain, Turkey and countries such as the Czech Republic, Greece, Great Britain, Ireland and Romania have a smaller share of trade.

Graph 2. Natural gas, million cubic metersAmount, thousand US dollars

Source: <https://www.stat.gov.az/source/trade/>

Azerbaijan's 2023 data shows that the main importers were Italy and Turkey. Italy imported 10,705.5 million cubic meters of natural gas worth 8.05 billion US dollars, which is a significant part of the total export value. Turkey exported 3.68 billion US dollars. Georgia, Bulgaria and Greece had a share of 900 million US dollars for 1117.5 million cubic meters. "Other countries" imported 522.2 million cubic meters worth 227 million dollars.

Conclusion

Unlocking Trade Opportunities indicates that developing nation producers can now capitalize on evolving consumption and production patterns. The objective is to expand the number of firms and economies in developing countries that can convert this inherent potential into tangible financial, social, and environmental benefits. Essential action items encompass:

- Gathering data and formulating statistics to comprehend market trends in critical sectors and services influenced by sustainable consumption and production. Enhancing comprehension of the essential components for effective collaborations among business, environmental, and developmental organizations, as well as governmental bodies, through the formulation of best practice checklists.
- Directing development aid towards exporters in developing nations striving to enhance their performance, particularly small and medium-sized firms.
- Advocating for autonomous validation of standards and ethical guidelines. Retailers in developed nations bear a significant obligation to furnish precise information to the end consumer.
- Promoting enhanced integration of the social and environmental aspects of commerce through the exchange of experiences among prominent corpora-

tions, environmental, development, and consumer organizations. Enhancing market access for exports from developing countries in industrialized markets, especially in the agricultural and textile sectors.

- Evaluating and eliminating rules in industrialized nations that obstruct access to sustainably produced products from developing countries.
- Reforming subsidies in wealthy and developing nations to establish equitable conditions for sustainable consumption and production.
- Formulating rules in industrialized nations for transparency, consultation, and the gradual implementation of new environmental regulations.

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